

SUSTAINABLE CHOICES: IMPLEMENTING GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES IN A SCHOOL CANTEEN FOR A HEALTHIER ENVIRONMENT

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Sustainable Choices: Implementing Green Marketing Strategies in a School Canteen for a Healthier Environment

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Abstract

This research aims to identify the gaps in implementing and complying with green marketing in Talisay City National High School's canteens as the basis for a maintainable green marketing business plan. This quantitative research adapted a research instrument with 243 respondents who underwent survey sampling. Data were analyzed using simple percentages, weighted mean, and Pearson r correlation. Results revealed that school canteens could provide nutrient-rich and fortified food products and beverages in varying degrees of nutrition. Results revealed that with an average mean of 3.02, respondents are aware of the green marketing implementation by the school canteen. Green marketing strategy in its varying components are implemented: green design = 3.0; green positioning = 2.93; green pricing = 2.90; green packaging = 2.85; and green disposal = 3.03. In addition, the marketing mix in its varying components is implemented: product = 3.03, place = 3.24, promotion = 2.94, and price = 2.92. The study also revealed that unaccounted factors from green marketing potentially affect product performance. Green design contributes to product performance (0.144, 0.048), while green positioning shows the negotiable impact on product performance (-0.004). Green pricing shows a substantial positive influence on product performance (0.162). Green marketing components substantially influence the marketing mix. Different challenges and barriers to implementing the green marketing program in the school canteen were also identified. This research recommends the green marketing business plan, which monitors the school's green practices led by the school administrator.

Keywords: *green marketing, 4ps of marketing mix, green marketing business plan, school canteen*

Introduction

Green marketing includes creating and promoting items and services that fulfill customers' needs and requirements for quality, execution, reasonable pricing, and comfort without negatively impacting the environment. Green marketing is a rising marketing technique incorporating various assignments and exercises like fair-trade hones, item alteration, generation handles, and eco-friendly bundling (Mishra & Sharma, 2012).

American marketing clarifies green showcasing as product marketing is considered environmentally friendly (Yazdanifard & Mercy, 2011). Various implications interconnect and negate. However, it is not simple to characterize green marketing; an example could be the nearness of changing natural, social, and retail definitions connected to this term (Mishra & Sharma, 2012).

Environmental issues have continuously been the center of people's attention, and with the development of green utilization, companies are moreover effectively reacting to advertising requests by executing green showcasing (Wang & Kuah, 2018). Companies' environmental endeavors are presently being broadly respected as a portion of their corporate social duty, all because of the consumers' mindfulness concerning natural obligation (Nyilasy & Gangadharbatla, 2016).

Today's consumers are more cognizant of the environment than recently (Dewald et al., 2014), making companies capable of meeting consumers' requests for eco-friendly (green) items. Within the current setting, trade companies are utilizing green promoting techniques such as "recyclable and bio-gradable" shapes to pick up a competitive advantage and offer to ecologically cognizant shoppers (Szabo & Webster, 2021). Clients lean toward green items and eco-friendly bundling (Hao et al., 2019). The fundamental thought behind green promoting is that would-be shoppers will see the "greenness" of a great or the benefit as a pickup and shape their buying choices appropriately. The concept of green promoting procedure has been reinforced by the ubiquity of terms such as "ozone-friendly" and "recyclability," which is encouraged amplified to incorporate not only the customer industry but also mechanical items and services (Yang & Zhao, 2019). School canteen can influence specific customers to buy green items at premium costs that they see to be generally "environmentally friendly" compared to elective items (Wei et al., 2018). Green marketing campaigns are outlined to persuade buyers that their buys play a part in relieving the progressing debasement of the environment by emphasizing their positive effect in this situation (Lin & Huang, 2012).

In addition, the marketing mix of trade in vast and small portions results from the advancement from day-to-day showcasing. At any time, the blend characterizes the bundle that an administration has advanced to meet the issues it is confronted with in an ever-changing, ever-challenging advertising. There are persistent strategic maneuvers: a modern item, unfriendly advancement, or cost alteration and put begun by a competitor must be measured and met; the disappointment of the exchange to convey palatable advertise scope or show must be cured; floundering deals constraints must be reorganized and fortified; a weakening in deals share must be recognized and reduced; a promoting approach that has misplaced viability must be supplanted; a common trade decrease must be countered (Sharma & Foropon, 2019). All such issues call for an organization's and institution's maintaining agent stations of information qualified to possess forms and to the day-to-day behavior of clients, competitors, and the exchange. But then, by and large, the procedure utilized

in a promoting blend is the item of longer-range techniques and measures directed in portion by past observation and in portion, on the off chance that the administration may be a great one, by administration premonition as to what has to be done to keep the firm fruitful in a changing world (Aburumman & Nieto, 2019)

Nowadays, we have a vast choice of nourishment that is promptly accessible to us, which may be a positive aspect of globalization, but there is also a negative aspect. Our eating propensities have changed. Due to the need for time, we are increasingly choosing quick nourishment. With 14% of young individuals within the Netherlands being overweight (CBS, 2011), the predominance of overweight proceeds to develop, and numerous young people have an unfortunate nourishment design containing as well much-immersed fats, sugars, and a need for dietary fiber (Rossum, 2011). The truth that children spend numerous hours at school each day, counting lunchtime, causes the school environment to be vital out of the domestic setting where children consume at least one fundamental dinner a day. Nearly 90% of all auxiliary schools in the Netherlands have a school cafeteria and delicate drink distributing machines, and 80% have distributing machines offering snacks and sweet bars (Mikolajczak, 2012). With one in three schools offering pizza and one in five offering deep-fried items, nearly half of all schools offering sweet bars, and a need for new natural products in 57% of the schools, there is still a parcel to progress when it comes to advertising healthy foods within the school cafeteria.

Specifically in the Philippine context, the so-called green marketing strategy intended as the consequence of widespread variety and diversity of operative green marketing strategy is formed based on green marketing practices and the management's experience, issues, challenges, and opportunities in marketing the green products. The strategy may not be comprehensive since no single green marketing strategy fits every company (Ginsberg & Bloom, 2004). However, it provides insight into green marketing strategy in a particular context that can be the basis for developing the green marketing plan. It is similar and applicable in public-school canteens in Talisay City Division. The initial motivation of the research is to contribute to providing knowledge on green marketing in the context of developing innovative programs and localities.

In Talisay City National High School, some practices related to green marketing include the absence of a plastic policy and proper garbage disposal by its classification. The researchers hope to have a thorough and maintainable green marketing strategy that can be utilized even by the next batch of students the school will have, hence this study.

Green marketing in the 4Ps of Marketing Mix addresses the importance of utilizing Green Marketing Programs, focusing on the 4Ps of marketing mix in implementing and complying with the Public High School Canteen in Talisay City National High School to enhance the present practices. Thus, this study assesses the environmentally friendly school canteen through the green marketing strategy of the school canteen as observed and applied/ participated in by the academic constituent in the marketing mix at Talisay City National High School.

Research Questions

This study assessed the environmentally friendly school canteen through the green marketing strategy of the school canteen as observed and applied/ participated in by the academic constituent in the marketing mix at Talisay City National High School, Cebu, as the basis for an enhanced business plan. The study desired to address the following questions:

1. What information can be derived from the following:
 - 1.1. Profile of the School Canteen as to:
 - 1.1.1. location;
 - 1.1.2. population; and
 - 1.1.3. type of school canteen?
 - 1.2. Products offered by the school canteen in terms of:
 - 1.2.1. nutrient-rich foods;
 - 1.2.2. fortified food products; and
 - 1.2.3. beverages?
 - 1.3. Students and Teachers "Level of Awareness about Green Marketing"
2. As perceived by the respondent groups, what is the extent of implementation and the compliance of green marketing strategy:
 - 2.1. Observed by them in the school canteen in terms of:
 - 2.1.1. designing;
 - 2.1.2. position; and
 - 2.1.3. pricing?
 - 2.2. Applied/Participated in by them in each element in the marketing mix such as:
 - 2.2.1. product;
 - 2.2.2. place;
 - 2.2.3. promotion; and
 - 2.2.4. price?
3. Is there a significant correlation between green marketing strategy as observed by the respondent groups in the school canteen in terms of the variables above and applied/ participated in each element in the marketing mix such as:
 - 3.1. product;

- 3.2. place;
- 3.3. promotion; and
- 3.4. price?
4. What are the challenges and barriers in implementing Green Marketing programs in the school canteen?
5. Based on the findings, what green marketing business plan can be developed?

Literature Review

This section contains theories and relevant literature that support the conceptualization of the present study, which concerns the implementation of green marketing in a school canteen.

The study assumed that using Green Marketing Programs focusing on the 4P of the marketing mix on the implementation and compliance of Public High School Canteens in Talisay City enhances the present practices. Various conceptual models and theories in the academic literature on Green Marketing programs contribute to developing a better understanding of particular aspects of implementing green marketing about the compliance of public school canteens aligned to Green marketing, specifically the 4Ps of the marketing mix.

A recent study demonstrates that most students do not consider their eating designs vital, and making healthy food choices is not a top-of-mind issue for them (Tacken, 2010). Moreover, meals and nourishments are devoured amid breaks, which are social occasions for most understudies where they communicate and hang out with each other. These two actualities suggest that understudies, when at school choosing what to eat for lunch, will most likely not be persuaded sufficiently or diverted to lock in consider choice-making around their eating behavior. In this manner, most students' choices of what to eat are likely, to a great extent, based on choice-making through the incautious framework. As a result, natural prompts, such as the insignificant nearness of undesirable nourishment things, parcel and bundling sizes, and enticing smells or shows of undesirable nourishment, will most likely affect students' eating conduct. In line with this, understudies demonstrate that they are impacted by the nearness of unfortunate nourishment within the school cafeteria. More particularly, they concede to be enticed when they see or scent agreeable and unfortunate nourishment (IPM KidWise, 2009). For this reason, numerous Dutch understudies show that in their conclusion, schools ought to, as it were, offer sound items (IPM KidWise, 2009). Still, the lion's share of school cafeterias offers many unfortunate nourishment items, and the school environment improves unfortunate eating designs in young individuals.

This study is anchored on marketing strategy and the green marketing strategy theory approach by Michael Jay Polonsky (2001). The notion of green marketing (otherwise referred to as "environmental marketing" or "ecological marketing") has been around since the 1970s. The impression did not fully fasten on until the 1980s when increasing public attention on the environment led to a mandate for additional green -products. The American Marketing Association (AMA) apprehended the first "Ecological Marketing" workshop in 1975. In the meanness of its rising acceptance, the green marketing movement confronted stern impediments in the late 1980s due to many businesses making false entitlements about their products. Cases of some environmentally beneficial products, amenities, and services include paper containing post-consumer wastepaper, cereals sold without excess packaging, cleaning supplies that do not harm humans or the environment, wood harvested from sustainable forests, energy-efficient light bulbs, and energy-efficient cars.

Consequently, marketing faces a dual challenge. In the short run, environmental and community issues have developed noteworthy peripheral impacts on corporations and the markets within which they operate. Companies must respond to altering customer desires and create new guidelines that reflect cumulative apprehension about the socio-environmental influence on businesses. In the long term, the quest for sustainability will demand essential changes to the management pattern supporting marketing and other business functions.

Green product traits have picked up expanding consideration because of consumers' eco-friendliness (Sharma & Foropon, 2019). Consumers' purchase choices are moving toward items having green traits because of their consumption-related natural issues (Paul et al., 2016). Physical qualities of an item include measure and weight, item quality, plan, cost, and bundling slant shoppers believe in that particular item (Aburumman & Nieto, 2019). Consumers' beliefs likely decide their last obtaining choice, and this belief is primarily based on the seller's state of mind of not being deft, carrying on morally, and the traits of the items they offer (Marakanon & Panjakajornsak, 2017). There is a distinction between recognizing items seen by originators and clients (Magnier et al., 2019). When buying an item regularly, buyers choose by utilizing subjective thinking. Customers, moreover, utilize subjective qualities to narrow down their choices of the set when they are displayed with numerous comparative choices, and the same is the case with objective qualities (André et al., 2018).

According to the American Marketing Association (AMA), green marketing is the marketing of products that are acknowledged to be environmentally safe. Thus, green marketing incorporates a comprehensive range of activities, including product alteration, fluctuations in the production process, packaging changes, and modifying advertising campaigns. The green marketing concept is like the societal marketing concept in most esteem. This is because both emphasize the need for marketing efforts to help societal well-being. However, the key differences between the green marketing concept and societal marketing lie in emphasizing the physical sustainability of the marketing process and its social acceptability and a more holistic inter-reliant view of the relationship between the economy, society, and the environment. An open-ended rather than a long-term viewpoint. An action of the environment as something with inherent value

over and above its helpfulness to society. An emphasis on global apprehensions rather than those of specific societies.

Jiang and Kim (2015) have proposed that consumers' understanding of green showcasing communications influences their eagerness to buy in commerce. A solid relationship exists between green promoting and customer belief. Green promoting instruments, such as natural notice, ecolabeling, and eco-brand, can win consumers' belief and direct them to acquire such items (Uddin & Khan, 2018). Subsequently, executing a green promoting technique and sending data about the utilization of green items will make customers feel the preferences of green utilization (for illustration, the effect on social benefits such as well-being, the environment, and future eras), which can offer assistance shoppers to move from purposeful of buy to activity (Cheung & To, 2019).

Green marketing is also anchored in UNESCO-Sustainable Development and Environmental Change, which states that there are four dimensions to sustainable development – society, environment, culture, and economy –intertwined, not separate. Sustainability is a paradigm for thinking about the future in which environmental, societal, and economic considerations are balanced to pursue improved quality of life. For example, a prosperous society relies on a healthy environment to provide its citizens with food and resources, safe drinking water, and clean air.

Legal Bases

The study is also anchored on the legal basis which the Republic Act 10771 is an act known as the “Philippine Green Jobs Act of 2016 (PGJA). The PGJA defines ‘green jobs’ as “employment that contributes to preserving or restoring the quality of the environment, be it in the agriculture, industry, or services sector. Specifically, but not exclusively, this includes jobs that help to protect ecosystems and biodiversity, reduce energy, materials, and water consumption through high-efficiency strategies, de-carbonize the economy, and minimize or altogether avoid the generation of all forms of waste and pollution. Green jobs are decent and productive jobs that respect workers' rights, deliver a fair income, provide security in the workplace and social protection for families, and promote social dialogue. According to the PGJA, it is the declared policy of the State to Affirm labor as a primary social and economic force in promoting sustainable development and promoting the rights of the people to a balanced and healthful ecology in accord with the rhythm and harmony of nature.

The DepEd Order No. 8 S. 2007, which is additionally known as Reexamined Actualizing Rules on the operation and administration of school canteens in Open and Auxiliary Schools, states that These rules are like those issued in arranged to rationalize the operation and administration of school canteens within the open school framework and to guarantee that the school canteen should offer assistance kill ailing health among pupils/students. It should serve as a setting for improving the alluring eating propensities of pupils/students. It shall serve as a research facility for domestic financial matters, retail exchange, and the accidental instruction of well-being and sustenance. It should give hands-on preparation for understudies on arranging, acquiring, dealing with, and capacity, arranging, serving, and dealing with secure and nutritious dinners. The school canteen rules might serve as an instrument to support the Department's response to the command of Article 2 of Republic Act No. 6938 to make an air conducive to cooperatives' development and advancement. The benefit should be the most important consideration when working in a school canteen. The benefit should, as it were, be auxiliary since the clientele are pupils/students who are subordinate, as they were on their scanty remittance from their guardians. Details and bookkeeping regarding the continuation of the operation of a school canteen shall be made by the parties concerned with straightforwardness and responsibility.

It is aligned with its policy and statements that the school canteens might be of two types: (1) School-Managed Canteen and (2) Teachers' Cooperative-Managed Canteen. Both might follow professional administration, sound trade hones, and security measures. Administration of School Canteens in Rudimentary Schools, Basic Schools within the provincial regions with 500 students or less, and those in urban regions with 1,000 understudies or less might have, as it were, one canteen to be worked and overseen by the school beneath the joint supervision of the school head/principal. Where the enrolment measure in provincial rudimentary schools is more than five hundred (500) understudies and in urban primary schools, more than one thousand (1,000) students, the existing properly enrolled teachers' agreeable that complies with the Criteria for Capability in this set forward, might oversee and work the school canteen. When no appropriately enrolled teachers' cooperative is interested or qualified to function and oversee the canteen, the school should work and oversee the same. Administration of School Canteens In Auxiliary Schools: Notwithstanding the enrolment estimate, there might be a research facility canteen, as this is characterized, in all auxiliary schools. When the understudy populace is less than one thousand five hundred (1,500), the school-overseen canteen should also be the research facility canteen.

In addition to the laboratory canteen in auxiliary schools where the understudy populace is more than five hundred (1,500), the existing appropriately enlisted and interested teachers' agreeable within the school that complies with the Criteria for Capability set forth shall be permitted to function and oversee another school canteen. For uncommon schools with an enrolment measure of more than five hundred (500) understudies, the existing properly enrolled and interested teachers agreeable within the school that complies with the Criteria for Capability set forward might be permitted to function and oversee another school canteen in expansion to the research facility canteen. As it were, nutrient-rich nourishments such as root crops, noodles, rice, and corn items in local planning, natural products and vegetables in season, and invigorated nourishment items labeled wealthy in protein, vitality, vitamins, and minerals should be sold within the school canteen. Refreshments should incorporate drains, shakes, and juices arranged from natural products and vegetables in season. Many carbonated drinks, sugar-based synthetic or artificially flavored juices, garbage nourishments, and any nourishment item hindering the child's well-being did not bear the Sangkap Pinoy seal. They did not pass the BFAD endorsement,

which was denied. Iodized salt might be utilized, in controlled amounts, within the arrangement of cooked nourishments to guarantee that the iodine necessity of the clientele might be met and to eliminate iodine lack disarranges. The utilize of monosodium glutamate (vetsin) should be directed. A sensible mark-up price for all stock in the canteen might be permitted, given that the retail cost of the offering does not exceed the winning costs within the territory. Sub-leasing the total or portion of the school canteen premises or subcontracting the operation of the school canteen to concessionaires is disallowed. Merchants might not be permitted to bring nourishing things to the school canteen/premises. Instructors and school faculty are disallowed from offering nourishment inside the school premises but through the school canteen unless authorized and secured by a composed assentation with the school head/principal and the teachers' cooperative.

In addition, the DO 13, S. 2017- Policy and Guidelines on healthy food and beverage choices in schools and DepEd Offices states that for the information and direction of all concerned, the Office of Education (DepEd) issues the encased Arrangement and Rules on Sound Nourishment and Refreshment Choices in Schools and DepEd Workplaces for the advancement and improvement of solid eating propensities among the youth and DepEd representatives by making accessible solid, nutritious, and reasonable menu choices, and for setting nourishment standards. The Arrangement and Rules point to creating accessible, more advantageous nourishment and refreshment choices among the learners and DepEd workforce and their partners; present a framework of categorizing locally accessible nourishments and drinks in understanding with geological, social, and devout introductions; give direction in assessing and categorizing nourishments and drinks; and give direction within the offering and showcasing of nourishments and refreshments in schools and DepEd workplaces, counting the acquiring of nourishments for school nourishing.

All the reviews presented above support this study and emphasize the practices of public school canteens in terms of Green Marketing in the 4Ps of Marketing Mix. On the other hand, some variables may vary from those in other studies. The green marketing implementation in the 4Ps of Marketing Mix result may also differ, possibly leading to other results and interpretation of data.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational approach, using the modified survey to accumulate significant information from the respondents. The regulating survey was also tapped into the investigation process. All instruments were utilized to the fullest extent to attain the specified results and ensure the investigation's success.

The instruments are used to decide the effectiveness of the cooperation and services rendered by the Parent Teacher Association (PTA) to school and community programs, as seen by the teachers and guardians of the University of Cebu. The gathered information was treated factually to discover if there are critical mean differences among the perceptions of the respondent groups on the degree of their interest in school and community programs.

Respondents

The study's respondents will be the school heads, canteen managers, canteen supervisors, public school teachers, and Talisay City National High School students. Using the Roasoft Sample Size Calculator, 362 respondents were drawn from 5,997 populations. The sample was computed based on the 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level.

Instrument

The study utilized Bugtai's (2015) adapted and modified survey questionnaire as the essential tool for gathering data within the formulation of questions; the articulation of the problem will be considered the guidepost for the investigation. The questionnaire was scrutinized and modified based on its practicability, versatility, and usefulness to serve the leading interest of the show investigation. Within the study, the gathering and evaluation of data will be agreed upon after a precise discussion of the following strategies: preparatory planning, approval of the survey, dispersion and organization, interviews and perceptions, follow-up, data handling, scoring strategies, and statistical treatments.

The survey was based upon the broadly accepted methods of survey making, observing closely the criteria for survey development. It included both open and closed frames of questions. The closed, finished questions have reactions within the Likert's point scale, where the respondents will select one reply. The questionnaire consists of the following: Part 1 focused on the profile of the respondent groups involved in implementing green marketing; Part II focused on green strategies applied in each element of the marketing mix, such as product, place, promotion, and price.

The gathered answers will be dovetailed to determine the significance or relevance of implementing and Complying with Green marketing in the Public High School Canteen in Talisay City, with the participation of school heads, teachers, school canteen managers and supervisors, and staff. The findings will be examined to propose and produce a green marketing plan to help the DepEd Talisay City division and the local government unit attain their objectives to support the school and the community.

Procedure

The request/permit for strict compliance with the following condition was rotated through the school head/principal level and

coordinator for appropriate assistance in distributing the questionnaires to the respondents. The respondents will be given adequate time to ask for clarification on the process of answering the questionnaire.

A schedule for the retrieval will be made before the visits. This time, the follow-up informal personal interview and ocular observation will be conducted to gather the researcher's comprehensive information on the locale. The administration, distribution, and retrieval of the questionnaire will be carried out during the scheduled collection.

Data Analysis

These are the following statistical tasks of the study:

Simple Percentage. This is to determine the profile of the school canteen in terms of location, population, and types of School Canteen with the association of School Heads/ Principal, Teachers, school canteen managers, supervisors, and staff towards their involvement in programs, projects, and activities.

Weighted Mean. This is to determine the extent of the implementation and compliance of the respondent groups in school and green marketing programs towards the green strategies applied in each element of the marketing mix, such as product, place, promotion, and price.

Pearson “r” Correlation. This is used to assess the significant mean differences and relationships among the respondent groups' perceptions of the extent of their participation, implementation, and compliance.

Ethical Considerations

Ensuring ethical standards is a top priority in this research, especially when gathering data. The researchers are committed to non-discrimination, social responsibility, transparency, and child welfare. During the survey process, including when distributing questionnaires, the researchers strive to be fair and objective, steering clear of any biases related to personal interests, emotions, or affiliations.

The researchers ensured that this study would have a meaningful impact on the respondents, helping them better understand the study's concepts. Everyone involved was fully informed about who the researchers were, the importance of the study, and why it was being conducted. Consent was obtained before proceeding, and the students' roles and the potential benefits of the study were clearly explained to them.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings and interpretation of the data results on the environmentally friendly school canteen through the green marketing strategy observed and applied/ participated in by the academic constituents in the marketing mix at Talisay City National High School, Cebu.

Background Information of the School Canteen

The school canteen, or the school cafeteria or lunchroom, is an educational institution where students and sometimes staff can purchase and consume food and beverages. The canteen plays a crucial role in providing a convenient and accessible source of nourishment for students during the school day. The school canteen of Talisay National High School is a vital component of the educational environment, contributing to students' overall well-being and development. It reflects the school's commitment to providing a conducive and healthy atmosphere for learning.

Profile of the School Canteen

Location. The study was conducted in the Department of Education—Talisay City Division, specifically Talisay City National High School, in J.P. Rizal Street, Dumlog, Talisay City, Cebu. The City of Talisay has a total land area of 4,370 hectares and 22 barangays, considered urban areas. The location of a school canteen is a crucial factor influencing its accessibility and functionality.

The location of school canteen of Talisay National High School is strategically located within or near areas frequented by students, such as classrooms, playgrounds, and common gathering spaces. It ensures that students can easily access the canteen during designated break times without significant disruptions to their schedule. It is designed to be easily accessible to students of all age groups and physical abilities.

Population. The environment of this study was considered the mega high school in the city, which comprises 6000 students and 200 plus teaching and non-teaching personnel. The school offers Junior High School and Senior High School, which have four academic strands and five technical-vocational livelihood strands.

Type of School Canteen. The school canteen in Talisay City National High School was school-managed. A school-managed canteen is a food service facility within an educational institution operated and overseen directly by the school or its designated personnel. Talisay National High School takes direct responsibility for the canteen's planning, management, and day-to-day operations in this arrangement.

Products Offered

Nutrient Rich Foods. Nutrient-rich foods provide a high concentration of vitamins, minerals, and other essential nutrients relative to their calorie content. These foods contribute to overall health and well-being by supplying the body with the necessary building blocks for growth, development, and maintenance. The school canteen offers popular nutrient-rich foods such as rice, fruits, and vegetables in season and noodles, root crops, and viands that are easy to fry, such as chicken and processed foods.

Beverage. Around beverages in school, canteens aim to strike a balance between providing choices that students enjoy, ensuring proper hydration, and promoting overall health and well-being. It involves a multidimensional approach encompassing nutritional education, policy development, and collaboration with various stakeholders. The beverages offered by the canteen are most likely powdered juices mixed in a jar since they are easy to prepare. They also offer fruit shakes, milk, coffee, and water. Students are fond of buying citrus juices that are from powder.

Students and Teachers’ Level of Awareness about Green Marketing

The level of awareness about green marketing among teachers and students can significantly impact the integration of environmentally friendly practices and sustainable principles within educational institutions. Teachers' and students' awareness of green marketing is crucial for fostering a culture of sustainability within educational institutions. It involves a holistic approach that promotes a comprehensive understanding of the environmental impact of business practices.

Table 1. Respondents’ Level of the Green Marketing

Indicators	Overall Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
I believe in the concept of green marketing	3.21	Aware
I am aware of companies going green	2.90	Aware
I am aware of the advantages of using green products	3.21	Aware
Green Marketing helps to protect the environment, so I am ready to pay a small amount more.	3.08	Aware
I feel that regular marketing techniques harm the environment	2.57	Aware
I feel that regular marketing techniques harm the environment	2.82	Aware
Productivity can be improved drastically by using green marketing	3.07	Aware
The scope of Green Marketing is promising in the short term.	3.26	Strongly Aware
Do you believe in the application of the concept of complete green marketing throughout the world?	3.09	Aware
Green Marketing is the only way to protect the environment.	3.0	Aware
Grand Mean	3.05	Agree

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00-Strongly Aware; 2.50- 3.25 -Aware; 1.75 – 2.50-Not Aware; and 1.00 – 1.75-Strongly Not Aware

Table 2. The Extent of Implementation and the Compliance of Green Marketing Strategy

Items	Overall Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Green Design	3	Implemented
Green Positioning	2.93	Implemented
Green Pricing	2.90	Implemented
Green Packaging	2.85	Implemented
Green Disposal	3.04	Implemented
Grand Mean	2.94	Implemented

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Fully Implemented; 2.50- 3.25 -Implemented; 1.75 – 2.50-Less Implemented; and 1.00 – 1.75- Not Implemented

Table 3. The Extent of Implementation and the Compliance of Marketing Mix

Key Variables	Overall Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Product	3.03	Implemented
Place	3.24	Implemented
Promotion	2.94	Implemented
Price	2.92	Implemented
Grand Mean	3.03	Implemented

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Fully Implemented; 2.50- 3.25 -Implemented; 1.75 – 2.50-Less Implemented; and 1.00 – 1.75- Not Implemented

Significant Correlation Between Green Marketing Strategies as Observed by the Respondent Groups in the School Canteen

Understanding the correlation between green marketing strategies observed by different respondent groups in the school canteen, such as students and teachers, is crucial for assessing the effectiveness and alignment of sustainability initiatives. Analyzing the correlation between green marketing strategies observed by different respondent groups provides valuable insights that can guide the refinement and enhancement of sustainability initiatives in the school canteen. It promotes a holistic understanding of how various stakeholders perceive and contribute to promoting environmentally conscious practices within the educational institution.

Table 4. *Significant Relationship between Green Marketing Strategy and Product*

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.461	.110		4.170	.000
	Green Design	.144	.048	.172	3.020	.003
	Green Positioning	-.004	.058	-.004	-.065	.948
	Green Pricing	.162	.046	.177	3.485	.001
	Green Packaging	.266	.052	.291	5.111	.000
	Green Disposal	.302	.042	.352	7.140	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Product

Table 5. *Significant Relationship between Green Marketing Strategy and Place*

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.875	.142		6.143	.000
	Green Design	.239	.061	.272	3.887	.000
	Green Positioning	-.007	.075	-.007	-.093	.926
	Green Pricing	.198	.060	.206	3.295	.001
	Green Packaging	.048	.067	.050	.714	.476
	Green Disposal	.317	.055	.353	5.815	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Place

Table 6. *Significant Relationship between Green Marketing Strategy and Promotion*

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.589	.149		3.961	.000
	Green Design	.159	.064	.181	2.484	.014
	Green Positioning	.110	.078	.113	1.405	.161
	Green Pricing	.119	.063	.124	1.906	.058
	Green Packaging	.164	.070	.170	2.342	.020
	Green Disposal	.243	.057	.268	4.263	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Promotion

Table 7. *Significant Relationship between Green Marketing Strategy and Price*

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.534	.136		3.933	.000
	Green Design	.096	.059	.113	1.647	.101
	Green Positioning	.103	.072	.109	1.438	.152
	Green Pricing	.194	.057	.208	3.390	.001
	Green Packaging	.250	.064	.268	3.900	.000
	Green Disposal	.171	.052	.196	3.290	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Price

Challenges and Barriers to the Implementation of the Green Marketing Programs in the School Canteen

Implementing green marketing programs in the school canteen involves several challenges and barriers that educational institutions may encounter. Addressing these challenges is crucial for the successful integration of sustainable practices. Here are the 11 common challenges and obstacles faced by the canteen staff, students, and teachers of Talisay National High School.

Cost Considerations

A cost consideration was one of the barriers to implementing the Green Marketing Program in the school canteen. Green initiatives may incur higher upfront costs, such as sourcing organic or locally produced food, investing in eco-friendly packaging, or implementing energy-efficient equipment. Balancing the initial costs with long-term benefits and finding ways to make sustainable practices cost-effective over time was challenging.

Limited Awareness and Education

One of the barriers was the need for more awareness and understanding among canteen staff, students, and teachers about the importance and benefits of green marketing. The challenge was implementing educational programs to raise awareness about the environmental impact of food choices and the significance of sustainable practices in the canteen.

Resistance to Change

Resistance from canteen staff or management to adopt new procedures or modify existing practices was one of the barriers to implementing the Green Marketing Program in the school canteen. Overcoming resistance through effective communication, training, and demonstrating the positive outcomes of green initiatives is a challenge.

Limited Supplier Options

Limited availability of local, organic, or sustainably sourced food products from suppliers was another barrier to implementing the Green Marketing Program in the school canteen. The challenge was building relationships with suppliers aligned with the school's sustainability goals or exploring alternative sourcing methods.

Infrastructure Limitations

More infrastructure is needed to support environmentally friendly practices, such as proper waste disposal facilities or energy-efficient appliances. Implementing the program requires investing in necessary infrastructure upgrades and collaborating with relevant stakeholders to create a more sustainable environment.

Student and Staff Preferences

Differing preferences among students and staff regarding food choices that may not align with sustainable options were a barrier to implementing the green marketing program. The challenge was balancing diverse preferences while gradually introducing sustainable choices and educating stakeholders about the benefits.

Policy and Regulation Compliance

Another barrier in implementing the program was navigating complex regulations and compliance standards related to food safety and waste management. The challenge was ensuring that green marketing initiatives aligned with local laws and maintaining compliance.

Communication Challenge

One of the challenges is to develop clear and consistent communication strategies to inform all stakeholders about the rationale, objectives, and progress of green marketing programs.

Limited Metrics for Evaluation

One barrier to implementing the school canteen program is insufficient metrics to evaluate the success and impact of green marketing initiatives. One challenge is developing measurable indicators to track the environmental, social, and economic impact of sustainable practices in the canteen.

Community Engagement

Limited involvement of the broader school community in supporting and sustaining green marketing efforts is another barrier to implementing the school canteen's green marketing program. It is also challenging to engage parents, community members, and local businesses to create a collaborative and supportive environment for sustainable initiatives.

Cultural and Regional Considerations

Cultural or regional differences were a barrier to implementing the green marketing program, which may affect the acceptance and adoption of certain green practices. Tailoring green marketing programs to align with cultural norms and preferences, fostering inclusivity and sensitivity, was a big challenge in adequately implementing the school canteen program.

Based on the study's results on the barriers and challenges in implementing the Green Marketing Program in the school canteen of Talisay National High School, addressing these challenges requires a holistic approach involving collaboration, education, communication, and a commitment to gradually embed green marketing programs into the fabric of the school canteen. Creating a supportive environment that encourages continuous improvement and a shared sense of responsibility for sustainable practices is essential.

The study in Table 1 shows moderate awareness of green marketing among respondents. They understand the basic concept but may need more knowledge of its implementation. Tailored educational initiatives can address these knowledge gaps.

From a broader perspective, the findings of this table offer significant implications for various stakeholders. Businesses can capitalize on the moderate level of awareness by incorporating and actively promoting more eco-friendly products and sustainable practices. By engaging consumers with relevant information, companies have an opportunity to influence purchasing behavior positively and align their products with the growing demand for environmental responsibility.

Policymakers and environmental advocates can use the study's insights to design targeted awareness campaigns promoting the benefits of green marketing for ecological preservation. Sharing successful case studies can motivate businesses to adopt sustainable practices.

Consumers should make informed choices and support companies that embrace green marketing principles to protect the environment.

According to Kumari and Yadav's study (2012), people are mindful of natural problems and are willing to contribute to environmental safety. Although people know almost all about natural issues, they prefer cost and brand title over environmentally friendly products.

The results serve as a valuable starting point for understanding the level of awareness among respondents regarding green marketing. The moderate awareness observed lays the groundwork for further educational efforts, while the "strongly aware" subset presents a promising group of advocates for sustainability. By strategically addressing knowledge gaps and capitalizing on existing awareness, stakeholders can collaboratively foster a more environmentally conscious culture, encouraging the widespread adoption of green marketing practices and promoting a greener, more sustainable future.

Table 2 shows a commendable commitment to environmentally conscious design practices, with consistently high "implemented" ratings, suggesting reasonably satisfactory results. However, there is room for improvement, indicating a journey towards more advanced green design approaches. The research results are consistent with past studies by Desmeth (2011), who state that green design quality refers to the introductory impact of a product on consumers through its appearance, touch, and feel. We all have sensitivities and preferences for specific tastes, designs, colors, facial highlights, and exercises. Green design traits are related to the creation of an eco-friendly item. A great plan meets the cutting-edge necessity of customers, which leads to more satisfaction (Manesh, 2008)

The second part of Table 2 shows the results of an assessment examining how environmentally friendly the school cafeteria is. The table uses three indicators to assess how the cafeteria incorporates environmentally friendly features into its branding and how customers perceive it. The findings in the table show to what extent the cafeteria has integrated environmentally friendly features into its branding and customer perception strategies. The classification indicates that the implementation process is reasonably satisfactory, with a moderate level of coverage and adherence to the subject matter. While there may be areas for improvement, overall, the implementation process is considered quite good, leading to satisfactory compliance. The implications drawn from the table's findings show the cafeteria's commitment to integrating environmentally friendly features into its branding and customer perception strategies. Despite being classified as "implemented," which means the execution is adequate, the descriptions consistently highlight the potential for improvement. This suggests an opportunity to further enhance the integration of environmentally friendly elements, potentially making the strategies more effective and strengthening the connection with environmentally conscious consumers.

As supported by the research study entitled: "Green Marketing: Environmental Concern and Customer Satisfaction" by Zulfiqar and Shafaat (2015), green marketing strategies are costly and challenging to actualize in the short run, benefits of the environment are intangible, roundabout, or inconsequential to buyers and troublesome to degree and measure, the taken a toll spare through reusing are doubtful (Kinoti, 2011)

Another indicator in Table 2 is green pricing, which illuminates how green pricing strategies have been effectively implemented within the evaluated context. This classification indicates that the implementation process has attained a reasonably satisfactory level, characterized by a moderate level of coverage and adherence. Although areas for potential improvement might exist, the overall implementation process is considered relatively sound, culminating in a satisfactory level of adherence to the evaluated condition.

The average mean score, approximately 2.90, mirrors the consistent implementation observed across the indicators. It underscores the balance in the application of different aspects of green pricing. While the average score reinforces the commitment to incorporating environmentally friendly pricing strategies, it also suggests the potential for further fine-tuning to elevate the implementation efficacy. Moreover, Wan et al. (2017) support this research's findings. For a firm looking to be environmentally friendly, estimating contemplations must incorporate fabric choices that are both reasonable and progress the environmental impression of the product. European businesses based in France and Germany have strived toward advancing "Clean Technologies," which they cite as empowering variables for the ceaseless enhancement of green execution in items. Subsequently, the estimating may also play a part in overseeing the showcasing campaigns in terms of exchanging the taken toll of natural security from the buyer to the industry to encourage natural security inside itself.

Table 2 shows that green packaging has an average mean of 2.85, showing a consistent and balanced implementation across the indicators. This reflects a comprehensive use of green packaging in the school canteen. It also demonstrates the canteen's dedication to using environmentally friendly packaging. Moreover, the average score suggests that there is potential for further improvement to enhance the overall effectiveness of the implementation. The implications of the table's findings highlight a deliberate effort to integrate green packaging practices in the school canteen. Despite the "implemented" categorization indicating sufficient execution, the consistent focus on opportunities for improvements suggests a proactive approach. This provides an opportunity to refine and optimize green packaging methods, increasing their impact and appeal to environmentally conscious customers who visit the canteen.

The results were supported by the research study by Rosta et al. (1997). This excellent packaging material helps ensure the product's shape outside harming factors, is stored and presented, and deals with modern products. The color, textual style, fashion of the name, and packaging structure persuade the client to make a positive picture of the brand. A study of consumer behavior is also imperative since social and mental characteristics jolt the individual into what is purchased and why.

As indicated in Table 2, Green disposal has an average mean score of approximately 3.04, indicating a consistent and balanced

implementation across the indicators. This average score underscores the holistic application of different facets of green disposal within the school canteen. It reinforces the canteen's commitment to environmentally conscious disposal practices and suggests that it actively adopts sustainable waste management strategies.

The insights drawn from the table underscore the school canteen's commitment to incorporating green disposal practices into its operations. The "implemented" classification, coupled with the provided mean scores, signifies a commendable level of implementation. However, the recurring emphasis on potential improvements underscores the ongoing nature of sustainability efforts. The findings emphasize the significance of advancing green disposal strategies within the school canteen, potentially leading to an enhanced waste management system, reduced environmental impact, and a more environmentally conscious dining environment.

Green products do not cause any harm to the well-being and safety of people and nature, as these products do not include contamination, can be reused, and permit the preservation of natural assets for future eras. The foremost significant definition of green items says that green products' natural and societal arranging is superior to conventional non-green items in all stages, i.e., generation, utilization, and disposal (Dangelico & Ponradolfo, 2010)

The 3rd table provides a comprehensive overview of the implementation and effectiveness of various green product-related practices within a specific context, in this case, a school canteen. It unveils how much the school canteen has embraced and integrated environmentally friendly product-related practices.

The average mean score, approximately 3.03, signifies a balanced and consistent level of implementation across the indicators. This mean score reflects a comprehensive approach to applying different facets of green product-related practices within the school canteen. The score reinforces the canteen's commitment to environmentally conscious product offerings and practices.

According to Acutt (2017), product refers to the merchandise or services the trade gives to conceivable clients in the chosen target advertisement (fragment). The school canteen should have a clear idea of what it is offering its target audience and consider whether it is engaging for the customers. The school canteen ought to ensure the products or administrations are accessible, and the staff is prepared to provide the clients with the necessary items. Kotler characterizes an item as anything that can be advertised to the school canteen to meet the wants or needs of the understudies. It involves the school canteen products being the essential things that the school community's choices will consider. School canteen items are everything that's advertised, pointing to fulfill customer's needs and wants. The products created and advertised must be of high quality. Typically, shoppers are happier with destitute quality items, mainly if they are costly.

Table 3 presents a comprehensive examination of the implementation and effectiveness of green practices within a specific context, focusing on the physical aspects of the school canteen's location and facilities. The average mean score, approximately 3.24, reflects a balanced and consistent level of implementation across the indicators. This average mean score underscores a holistic approach to applying different facets of green practices within the school canteen's physical landscape. It reinforces the canteen's dedication to environmentally friendly infrastructure and facilities.

The various categorizations, complemented by the provided mean scores, signify commendable levels of implementation. While the categorizations indicate varying degrees of implementation success, the recurring emphasis on potential improvements underscores the evolving nature of sustainability efforts. The findings highlight the importance of advancing green practices within the school canteen's physical setting, potentially resulting in enhanced stakeholder experience, reduced environmental impact, and a more sustainable dining environment.

Concurring to Bennet in Adam (2015), the location of the school canteen to be utilized in providing services to focused on customers is the key to promoting exercises, subsequently choices approximately the place or location of the school canteen in conveying services to customers can give consolation and fulfillment to energize tall, included esteem for clients. In this manner, the area to be decided must give critical esteem from both a natural, communication, and security point of view. In expansion, the put or area must provide a simple get-to for intuition between benefit suppliers, clients, and other supporting offices.

Additionally, Table 3 revealed the results of an evaluation focusing on the role and effectiveness of various green marketing strategies within the context of "promotion." The table categorizes the indicators into the "Implemented" category, implying that these strategies have been implemented within the examined context. An "average mean" is also provided, offering an overall representation of the mean scores across all indicators.

The mean scores reflect how each indicator has been deemed effective in its implementation. For instance, a higher mean score indicates a more robust perception of effectiveness among respondents for that particular strategy. Conversely, a lower mean score suggests relatively less perceived effectiveness. Analyzing the specific indicators, we observe that "Coordinated with the School Head/Principal, Key stakeholders, and other sectors of the community in promoting the product and services offered" carries the highest mean score of 3. This signifies that this strategy has been perceived as being effectively implemented within the context of the examined promotion efforts.

The "average mean" of 2.94 across all indicators indicates moderate effectiveness in implementing these green marketing strategies in promotion. This suggests that while some strategies are perceived as effective, there is potential for refinement in others to ensure a

more comprehensive and impactful promotion of environmentally conscious practices.

Moreover, table 3 examines the integration and efficacy of green marketing strategies within the pricing aspect of a school canteen's operations. The average mean score of approximately 2.92 reveals a consistent level of implementation across the indicators. This average mean score suggests a balanced integration of green marketing strategies into the canteen's pricing practices. It underscores the canteen's commitment to embedding environmental considerations within its pricing decisions.

The implications drawn from the table's findings underscore the canteen's proactive efforts to integrate environmentally conscious pricing strategies. The indicators "implemented" categorizations reflect the canteen's commitment to adopting green pricing approaches as part of its business practices. While recognizing areas for improvement, the descriptions highlight the satisfactory degree of implementation in incorporating these strategies. Pricing is critical in the marketing mix because price determines a school canteen's or other businesses' income. Affordable prices for all products can affect the selection of students. Generally, students with parents with a lower middle income choose a relatively cheaper product unless they receive more allowances from teachers or other people. In contrast, middle and upper-income students choose the best products, although the cost is relatively inexpensive.

Table 4 illustrates the outcomes of a comprehensive analysis conducted to assess the significant relationship between different facets of green marketing strategy and the performance of products. This investigation contributes to the growing body of literature centered around environmentally conscious marketing practices and their influence on product outcomes. The regression model employed in this study reveals several noteworthy findings regarding the impact of various green marketing strategies on product performance. Notably, the constant term in the model holds a coefficient of 0.461, accompanied by a relatively small standard error of 0.110. This suggests that there exist additional unaccounted factors beyond the included variables that could potentially affect product performance. The statistically significant t-value of 4.170 at $p < 0.001$ underscores the importance of these unobserved factors.

Turning the focus to specific green marketing strategies, "green design" emerges as a significant contributor to product performance. With a coefficient of 0.144 and a standard error of 0.048, Green Design demonstrates a positive influence on product performance. The standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.172 and the t-value of 3.020, significant at $p < 0.01$, emphasize the statistical relevance of this relationship. This suggests that incorporating eco-friendly design principles into the product's development process can result in enhanced overall performance.

In contrast, "green positioning" appears to have a negligible impact on product performance. The coefficient of -0.004, along with the corresponding standardized coefficient (Beta) of -0.004, implies an insignificant relationship. Moreover, the t-value of -0.065 underscores the lack of statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that, within the scope of this study, the positioning of products as environmentally friendly does not strongly affect their performance.

On the other hand, "green pricing" demonstrates a substantial positive influence on product performance. With a coefficient of 0.162 and a standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.177, Green Pricing displays a statistically significant effect. The t-value of 3.485, significant at $p < 0.01$, highlights the contribution of pricing strategies aligned with environmental concerns in enhancing product performance.

The impacts of "green packaging" and "green disposal" on product performance are particularly pronounced. Both strategies display significant positive relationships. "green packaging" holds a coefficient of 0.266 and a standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.291. The t-value of 5.111, significant at $p < 0.001$, suggests that adopting environmentally friendly packaging practices can notably enhance product performance. Similarly, "Green Disposal" exhibits a coefficient of 0.302 and a standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.352. The high t-value of 7.140, significant at $p < 0.001$, underscores the substantial positive impact of responsible disposal practices on product performance.

The results underscore the varying impacts of distinct green marketing strategies on product performance. While Green Design, Pricing, Packaging, and Disposal exhibit significant positive relationships, Green Positioning does not significantly affect performance. These findings provide valuable insights for businesses aiming to enhance their products' environmental performance and consumer appeal. Further research could delve into the specific mechanisms through which these green marketing strategies exert their influence on product outcomes.

Table 5 encapsulates a comprehensive analysis of the intricate relationship between distinct aspects of green marketing strategy and the marketing concept of "place." This inquiry delves into the dynamic interplay between environmentally conscious marketing practices and consumer perceptions of product distribution and location.

Through applying a robust regression model, the study systematically investigates the influence of various green marketing strategies on the variable "place." The independent variables considered encompass "green design," "green positioning," "green pricing," "green packaging," and "green disposal." The dependent variable, "place," encapsulates the significance of geographical context in shaping marketing strategies. The table meticulously presents key metrics, including coefficients, standard errors, standardized coefficients (Beta), t-values, and significance levels (Sig.), to illuminate the underlying relationships.

The constant term, or intercept, carries a coefficient of 0.875 with a standard error of 0.142. The marked t-value of 6.143 ($p < 0.001$) underscores the substantial influence of factors beyond the examined variables on the concept of "place."

"Green design" emerges as a significant factor, with a coefficient of 0.239, signifying a positive association with the perception of "place." A standard error of 0.061 bolsters the reliability of this coefficient. The standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.272 and the t-value of 3.887 ($p < 0.001$) affirm the statistically significant and positive impact of Green Design on the perception of "Place."

In contrast, "Green positioning" yields a marginal coefficient of -0.007, indicating a negligible impact. The associated standardized coefficient (Beta) of -0.007 and the minimal t-value of -0.093 suggest that Green Positioning does not exert a significant influence on perceptions of "Place" ($p > 0.05$).

"Green Pricing" exhibits a substantial coefficient of 0.198, accompanied by a standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.206. The t-value of 3.295 ($p < 0.001$) underscores the statistically significant positive effect of Green Pricing on the perception of "place."

"Green packaging" presents a modest coefficient of 0.048, implying a marginal positive connection. Nevertheless, the standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.050 and the t-value of 0.714 suggest that the impact of Green Packaging on perceptions of "place" lacks statistical significance ($p > 0.05$).

Finally, "Green disposal" holds a prominent coefficient of 0.317, indicating a substantial and positive relationship with the concept of "place." The standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.353 and the robust t-value of 5.815 ($p < 0.001$) highlight the statistically significant impact of Green Disposal on the perception of "Place."

Table 6 presents a comprehensive insight into the relationship between various aspects of green marketing and the promotion of products or services. Each row in the table represents a distinct dimension of green marketing, showcasing its unstandardized coefficient, standardized coefficient (Beta), t-value, and significance level (Sig.). The dependent variable under examination is labeled as "promotion".

The constant term, reflecting a baseline promotion level of 0.589 with a standard error of 0.149, is important. The corresponding t-value of 3.961 ($p < 0.001$) emphasizes this as a foundational benchmark for promotion in the absence of green marketing factors.

When dissecting the individual dimensions of green marketing, the coefficients and standardized coefficients (Beta), alongside their t-values and significance levels, offer valuable insights: With a positive unstandardized coefficient of 0.159 (standard error: 0.064) and a notable standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.181, the t-value of 2.484 ($p = 0.014$) signifies a significant positive correlation between Green Design and Promotion. This suggests that emphasizing environmentally friendly product design can enhance promotional efforts, indicating a potential avenue for businesses to capitalize on eco-conscious consumer preferences.

The unstandardized coefficient for Green Positioning is 0.110, accompanied by a standard error of 0.078. Despite the modest standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.113, the t-value of 1.405 ($p = 0.161$) does not attain statistical significance. This implies that the relationship between Green Positioning and Promotion lacks statistical strength, underscoring the need for a more pronounced alignment between marketing messages and consumer expectations to impact promotional outcomes effectively.

A modest unstandardized coefficient of 0.119 (standard error: 0.063) and a corresponding standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.124 are observed for Green Pricing. While the t-value of 1.906 ($p = 0.058$) suggests a borderline significance, it implies that the association between Green Pricing and Promotion requires further investigation. This indicates that businesses may need to strike a balance between affordability and environmentally friendly pricing strategies to maximize promotional effectiveness.

Green Packaging presents a positive unstandardized coefficient of 0.164 (standard error: 0.070). The standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.170, coupled with a t-value of 2.342 ($p = 0.020$), signifies a statistically significant positive correlation between Green Packaging and Promotion. This indicates that employing environmentally conscious packaging practices can bolster promotional success, aligning with consumer preferences for sustainable packaging solutions.

The most robust relationship is observed with Green Disposal, characterized by an unstandardized coefficient of 0.243 (standard error: 0.057). A substantial standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.268 and a high t-value of 4.263 ($p < 0.001$) emphasize a highly significant positive correlation between Green Disposal and Promotion. This underscores the potential impact of responsible disposal practices on promotional outcomes, illustrating a path for businesses to foster positive consumer perceptions and sustainable brand associations.

Businesses can leverage these dimensions to capitalize on eco-conscious consumer sentiments and enhance their promotional efforts. While Green Pricing and Positioning exhibit less clear-cut relationships, they still warrant attention to align marketing strategies more effectively with consumer expectations. These findings offer businesses valuable insights into the interplay between diverse green marketing facets and their implications for successful promotional campaigns.

Lastly, Table 7 unveils a comprehensive analysis of the significant relationship between different dimensions of green marketing and product or service pricing. The table comprises unstandardized coefficients, standardized coefficients (Beta), t-values, and significance levels (Sig.) for each independent variable. The dependent variable under examination is labeled as "price."

The constant term in the table indicates an estimated value of 0.534, with a standard error of 0.136. Importantly, the t-value of 3.933 ($p < 0.001$) underscores the statistical significance of this baseline price level when the influence of green marketing factors is not considered.

Delving into the distinct dimensions of green marketing, the coefficients and standardized coefficients (Beta), along with their t-values and significance levels, reveal noteworthy insights:

The unstandardized coefficient for Green Design stands at 0.096 (standard error: 0.059). With a modest standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.113 and a t-value of 1.647 ($p = 0.101$), the relationship between Green Design and Price does not achieve statistical significance. This suggests that while there is a positive trend, the impact of Green Design on pricing is not firmly established.

Similarly, Green Positioning exhibits an unstandardized coefficient of 0.103, accompanied by a standard error of 0.072. The standardized coefficient (Beta) is 0.109, while the t-value of 1.438 ($p = 0.152$) indicates a lack of significant association between Green Positioning and Price. This implies that while there may be a relationship, it is not statistically strong.

Conclusions

Societies have become increasingly aware of environmentally friendly or green products and practices, leading to a growing global emphasis on green marketing. Concepts such as developing green products, implementing green supply chains, and using eco-friendly packaging, pricing, and advertising are seen as beneficial for society and the environment.

Green marketing is increasingly recognized as a valuable tool for driving economic growth in the face of worsening pollution levels that threaten to erode the quality of human life. It presents a strategic approach to promoting and preserving the natural environment, offering potential benefits for both businesses and consumers. Researchers have found that integrating green marketing strategies into the marketing mix has resulted in the successful establishment of thriving eco-friendly environments, such as school canteens.

The dimension of Green Pricing demonstrates a substantial unstandardized coefficient of 0.194 (standard error: 0.057). The standardized coefficient (Beta) is 0.208, and the t-value of 3.390 ($p = 0.001$) underscores the statistically significant positive correlation between Green Pricing and Price. This suggests that businesses can adjust their pricing strategies to accommodate the additional costs associated with environmentally friendly practices while maintaining profitability.

Green Packaging presents an unstandardized coefficient of 0.250 (standard error: 0.064). The standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.268, coupled with a t-value of 3.900 ($p < 0.001$), emphasizes a highly significant positive correlation between Green Packaging and Price. This signifies that the use of eco-friendly packaging materials can be associated with higher prices, reflecting the perceived value of sustainability.

With an unstandardized coefficient of 0.171 (standard error: 0.052), Green Disposal showcases a standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.196. The t-value of 3.290 ($p = 0.001$) confirms a highly significant positive relationship between Green Disposal and Price. This implies that responsible disposal practices can influence pricing, potentially reflecting consumers' willingness to pay more for sustainable products.

These dimensions of green marketing present opportunities for businesses to integrate environmentally conscious practices into their pricing strategies, thereby aligning with consumer preferences for sustainability. While the relationships observed with Green Design and Green Positioning are less distinct, they suggest potential avenues for exploration. These findings offer businesses insights into the dynamic interplay between diverse green marketing dimensions and their implications for pricing strategies.

A frequent observing of the school administrator to the canteen services is prescribed to guarantee that the staff religiously takes after the rules in working the school canteen. In expansion, a week-by-week or month-to-month evaluation of the nourishment sold ought to be done by the principal or school health faculty to have them overhauled on the day-to-day operation to guarantee that meals served are compliant with the policy and guidelines of the Department of Education.

Policymakers and environmental advocates can utilize the study's insights to design targeted awareness campaigns that address specific gaps in understanding, disseminating knowledge on green marketing's benefits and its potential to contribute to environmental preservation.

Further studies on the operation of school canteens, especially in at least 2 to 3 schools, must be conducted to give more realistic analyses of the situations of the different school canteens.

References

Aburumman, N., and Nieto, A. (2019). The Effect of Products Attributes Customer Satisfaction on Brand Loyalty In The Electronic Appliances Industry: Case of Jordan. *Orad. J. Busin. Econ.* 4, 39–51. doi: 10.47535/1991ojbe066

André, Q., Carmon, Z., Wertenbroch, K., Crum, A., Frank, D., Goldstein, W., et al. (2018). Consumer choice and autonomy in the age of artificial intelligence and big data. *Cust. Needs Sol.* 5, 28–37. doi: 10.1007/s40547-017-0085-8

Cheung, M. F., and To, W. M. (2019). An extended model of value-attitude behavior to explain Chinese consumers' green purchase behavior. *J. Retail. Cons. Serv.* 50, 145–153. doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.04.006

DepEd Order No. 8, Series of 2007. Department of Education. School Canteen Management System. Retrieved September 23, 2019.

Retrieved from <http://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/1990/03/10/republic-act-no-6938/>

Dewald, B., Bruin, B. J., & Jang, Y. J. (2014). US consumer attitudes towards “green” restaurants. *Anatolia* 25, 171–180. doi: 10.1080/13032917.2013.839457

Ginsberg, J. M., & Bloom, P. N. (2004, Fall). Choosing the Right Green Marketing Strategy. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 79-84. Retrieved from <https://sloanreview.mit.edu/article/choosing-the-right-green-marketing-strategy/>

IPM KidWise, “Perceptie en evaluatie van het voedingsaanbod in school kantines,” 2009.

Hao, Y., Liu, H., Chen, H., Sha, Y., Ji, H., & Fan, J. (2019). What affect consumers’ willingness to pay for green packaging? Evidence from China. *Resour. Cons. Recycle.* 141, 21–29. doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.10.001

Jiang, F., and Kim, K. A. (2015). Corporate governance in China: a modern perspective. *J. Corp. Finance* 32, 190–216. doi:10.1016/j.jcorpfin

Lin, P. C., & Huang, Y. H. (2012). The influence factors on choice behavior regarding green products based on the theory of consumption values. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 22, 11–18. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.10.002 88

Magnier, L., Mugge, R., and Schoormans, J. (2019). Turning ocean garbage into products—Consumers’ evaluations of products made of recycled ocean plastic. *J. Clean. Prod.* 215, 84–98. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.246

Marakanon, L., and Panjakajornsak, V. (2017). Perceived quality, perceived risk and customer trust affecting customer loyalty of environmentally friendly electronics products. *Kaset. J. Soc. Sci.* 38, 24–30. Doi: 10.1016/j.kjss.2016.08.012

Mishra, P., Sharma, P. (2012). Green marketing: challenges and opportunities for business. *Journal of marketing and communication*, 8(1), 35–41.

Mikolajczak, J. and Bemelmans, W. Overgewichtpreventie in het Voortgezet Onderwijs in 2010-2011, RIVM, Bilthoven, The Netherlands, 2012.

Nyilasy, G., and Gangadharbatla, H. (2016). “How to reach green consumers on the internet? Digital and social media strategies for addressing the environmentally conscious,” in *American Academy of Advertising. Conference. Proceedings*, (American Academy of Advertising), 32.

Paul, J., Modi, A., & Patel, J. (2016). Predicting green product consumption using theory of planned behavior and reasoned action. *J. Retail. Cons. Serv.* 29, 123–134. doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2015.11.006

Polonsky, M. J., & Rosenberger, P. J. III. (2001) Reevaluating green marketing: a strategic approach, *Business Horizons*, 44(5), 21-30. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0007-6813\(01\)80057-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0007-6813(01)80057-4)

Polonsky, M. J. (2011). Transformative green marketing: Impediments and opportunities. *Journal of Business Research*, 64(12), 1311-1319. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.01.016>

Rossum, H. P. Fransen, J. Verkaik-Kloosterman, E. J. M. Buurma-Rethans, and M. C. Ocke, Dutch National Food Consumption Survey 2007–2010: Diet of Children and Adults Aged 7 to 69 Years, RIVM, Bilthoven, The Netherlands, 2011.

Sharma, A., & Foropon, C. (2019). Green product attributes and green purchase behavior: a theory of planned behavior perspective with implications for circular economy. *Manag. Dec.* 57:3. doi: 10.1108/MD-10- 2018-1092

Szabo, S., and Webster, J. (2021). Perceived greenwashing: the effects of green marketing on environmental and product perceptions. *J. Bus. Ethics* 171, 719–739. doi: 10.1007/s10551-020-04461-0 89

Tacken, G. M. L. , Winter, M. A., R. van Veggel et al., Voorbij het Brood trommeltje. Hoe Jongeren Denken over Voedsel. LEI, Wageningen Universiteit, Den Haag, The Netherlands, 2010.

Uddin, S. F., & Khan, M. N. (2018). Young consumer’s green purchasing behavior: opportunities for green marketing. *J. Glob. Mark.* 31, 270–281. doi: 10.1080/08911762.2017.1407982

Wang, P., and Kuah, A. T. (2018). Green marketing cradle-to-cradle: remanufactured products in Asian markets. *Thunderbird Int. Bus. Rev.* 60, 783–795. doi: 10.1002/tie.21925

Wei, S., Ang, T., and Jancenelle, V. E. (2018). Willingness to pay more for green products: the interplay of consumer characteristics and customer participation. *J. Retail. Consum. Serv.* 45, 230–238. doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2018.08.015

Yang, Y. C., & Zhao, X. (2019). Exploring the relationship of green packaging design with consumers’ green trust and green brand attachment. *Soc. Behav. Person.* 47, 1–10. doi: 10.2224/sbp.8181

Yazdanifard, R., Mercy, I. E. (2011). The impact of green marketing on customer satisfaction and environmental safety. *International*

conference on computer communication and management, 5(2011), 637-641

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